

A Comparative Analysis of the Most Prioritize Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Telkom Indonesia is a state-owned telecommunications company in Indonesia that operates in the telecommunications industry. As a digitally transformed telecommunications company, Telkom needs to be agile in facing the dynamics of the industry. Telkom Indonesia has launched Five Bold Moves, which are five major strategies, to become a world-class telecommunications (telco) company. In general, these five major strategies are implemented by investing in telecommunications infrastructure and digital platforms in a balanced manner to meet shareholder aspirations and address industry challenges, such as the sustainability of Telkom's business in the future and improving the company's valuation and profits.

The objective of this research is to determine the hierarchical structure of criteria, sub-criteria, and key alternatives in the selection of the Most Prioritized Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia. This study employs the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method with the assistance of the Expert Choice application. The research subjects are employees of Telkom Indonesia, and the number of participants in the study is 31.

The results of the research indicate that competitive advantage and strategic are the main criteria for selecting the Most Prioritized Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia. And for The main alternatives indicate that "fixed and mobile collaboration (FMC)" and "data center Co" have a dominant influence in the hierarchy structure. The suggestion that the researcher can convey related to the results of this study is to add alternatives to similar research and combine the Analytic Hierarchy Process method with other Multi Criteria Decision Making techniques enabling decision-makers to make informed choices regarding their implementation. This research contributes to the strategic management literature by offering a comparative analysis of Telkom Indonesia's five bold moves strategies using the AHP model. The findings provide valuable recommendations for Telkom Indonesia's management team and serve as a basis for further research in the field of strategic decision-making in the telecommunications industry.

KEYWORDS: Analytic Hierarchy Process, Five Bold Moves, Telecommunication Industry, Telkom Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

PT Telkom Indonesia Tbk continues to carry out its commitment to transform into a leading digital telco. Telkom is committed to actively contribute to the realization of a digitally independent and sovereign Indonesia. At least three domains need to be created, namely digital environment, digital society, and digital economy, to achieve digital sovereignty. Telkom Indonesia operates in a dynamic and rapidly changing telecommunications industry. To navigate this landscape successfully, companies must adopt strategies that are innovative and forward-thinking. Telkom focuses on developing its competence and capabilities in the digital business through three main pillars: digital connectivity, digital platform, and digital services. Telkom also has vision to create a more prosperous and competitive nation and provide the best added value for stakeholders, which is stated in the company's three missions, namely accelerating the development of digital infrastructure and platforms, developing superior digital talent, and orchestrating the digital ecosystem. The vision and mission launched by Telkom in 2019 is in line with the direction of the Minister of SOEs of the Republic of Indonesia. Telkom as a digital telecommunications company that acts as one of the backbones of Indonesia's digitalization must always innovative and collaborative to be able to realize an equitable digital ecosystem in the future. Telkom took this mandate as a motivation for companies to accelerate the transformation steps and become the locomotive of Indonesia's digitization drive. Telkom sees the digital potential as a great opportunity to continue support equity and improve the quality of digitalization that is taking place (Telkom, 2022).

Based on global facts followed by Telkom (2022), the telecommunications sector is facing various fundamental challenges such as negative headwinds, low revenue growth, increased capex investments, and stagnant profitability. These factors have an impact on the potential for low valuation improvement. Referring to benchmarks, the strategy of telco companies in responding to various challenges is the new trend in the telco business, which is business structure delayering. Delayering the business structure provides an opportunity to gain greater value compared to solely focusing on the integrated telco model, Telkom (2022). Most telco companies have similar assets/businesses that are owned by non-telco players. Generally, the growth and value generated from these assets/businesses are not maximized because they are locked within the integrated telco management model, where they are perceived as telco businesses. This creates a gap not only in capabilities but also in growth expectations, margins, and multiples. Currently, Telkom is increasing aggressively with the main strategy of Five Bold Moves to build the company's competitive advantages and leadership in the industry. The strategy includes the company's long-term plans and goals to become a world-class leading digital telco company that has a positive impact on all stakeholders and society. In general, the five major strategies are carried out by investing in telecommunication infrastructure and digital platforms in a balanced manner, to increase the company's valuation and profit. First, the Fixed & Mobile Convergence (FMC) strategy in which Telkom continues to strengthen market penetration, cost efficiency and operational excellence, in line with efforts to improve the best customer experience. Second, the Infra Co strategy is the Company's initiative to unlock the potential for consolidation of its infrastructure assets, including optical access network infrastructure and towers. Third, in the Data Center Co strategy, Telkom carries out the process of consolidating assets and increasing data center business capacity. Fourth, the B2B IT Service initiative which begins with transformation steps both internally and externally through partnerships and collaborations with technology companies. Finally, the fifth, the main strategy that will be realized by Telkom is to develop a digital company or DigiCo that focuses on the B2B and B2C business segments (Telkom,2022). Telkom as a digitalization locomotive in Indonesia will continue to be proactive in reading market potential and see various opportunities for various business expansions. The Five Bold Moves strategy is currently a priority for Telkom to strengthen the company's competitive advantages so that it can accelerate the realization of the vision to become the leading digital telco and create equitable digital sovereignty for the community for a better Indonesia. The five bold moves strategy is the company's effort to get maximum potential from the three business pillars that are carried out in order to maximize opportunities, increase competitiveness and value creation. Currently, Telkom does not have specific priorities among the five bold moves strategy because this strategy is still newly introduced and ongoing in the transition process. As the strategy is still in progress, it is essential for Telkom to carefully evaluate and prioritize the bold moves based on their potential impact and alignment with the company's long-term goals and market conditions. The author is interested in conducting an in-depth analysis by compiling a thesis entitled "A Comparative Analysis of The Most Effective Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia: An Analytical Hierarchy Process Model."

LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently, Telkom is undergoing a transformation agenda known as "5 Bold Moves." This transformation is being carried out in response to several key strategic challenges, namely industry challenges and shareholder aspirations. These challenges will determine the sustainability of Telkom's business in the future and accelerate the growth of the company's equity, while also fulfilling the shareholders' aspiration to increase the valuation by 600 trillion in 2024.

A. Five Bold Moves

Fixed Mobile Convergence (FMC): FMC is a strategy that aims to integrate fixed-line and mobile services, providing seamless connectivity and services to customers. By converging fixed-line and mobile networks, Telkom can offer bundled services, such as voice, data, and multimedia, across different devices and platforms. This strategy allows Telkom to enhance customer experience, increase operational efficiency, and capture new revenue opportunities. **InfraCo:** The InfraCo strategy involves the separation of Telkom's infrastructure assets into a separate infrastructure company. This move allows for greater focus on infrastructure development, optimization, and expansion. By establishing InfraCo, Telkom can efficiently manage and monetize its infrastructure assets, including fiber optic networks, towers, and data centers, while attracting potential investors for infrastructure partnerships and collaborations. **Data Center Co:** Telkom's Data Center Co strategy focuses on the development and expansion of data center services. With the increasing demand for cloud computing and data storage, Telkom aims to strengthen its position as a leading provider of data center facilities and services. By offering reliable, secure, and scalable data center solutions, Telkom can cater to the growing needs of businesses and organizations for hosting their critical applications and data.

B2B Digital IT Service Co: This strategy centers around the establishment of a Business-to-Business (B2B) Digital IT Service Company. Telkom aims to provide comprehensive digital IT services to enterprise customers, ranging from managed IT services, cloud solutions, cybersecurity, digital consulting, and other value-added services. This move enables Telkom to cater to the evolving digital needs of businesses and offer end-to-end digital solutions to enhance their productivity and competitiveness.

DigiCo: DigiCo refers to Telkom's digital content and services strategy. Telkom aims to expand its digital content offerings, including video streaming, music, gaming, and other digital entertainment services. By providing engaging and innovative digital content, Telkom can attract and retain customers, diversify its revenue streams, and tap into the growing digital entertainment market (Telkom, 2022)

B. Analytical Hierarchy Process

The Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) is a valuable approach for decision-making when confronted with multiple criteria and options. AHP simplifies the problem by creating a clear hierarchical structure to assess priorities and make choices among alternatives (Saaty, 1990). It is particularly effective in breaking down complex problems into a hierarchical format (Görener, 2012). Understanding the key principles of AHP (Saaty, 1995) is crucial: 1) Decomposition involves breaking the problem down into interconnected elements to form a hierarchical decision-making process; 2) Prioritization requires pairwise comparisons of each element in the hierarchy (Kuixiu, 2014) using a scale ranging from 1 to 9 (Saaty, 1994) to denote equal, weak, moderate, strong, and extreme preferences. Consistency ($CR \leq 0.1$) ensures the accuracy of ranking results; 3) Synthesis of priorities involves determining the hierarchical ranking; and 4) Logical consistency entails grouping elements in a coherent and relevant manner. For instance, if someone performs activity x twice as much as activity y, and chooses activity y twice as much as activity z, the systematic choice would be activity x four times more than activity z (Hartono et al., 2018).

C. Strategic Prioritization

Joshi et al. (2003) describe strategic priorities that are expected to be in harmony with and reinforce the strategies set at the business level. This alignment of priorities is believed to have a positive impact on overall organizational performance, while any lack of alignment is likely to have adverse effects on performance. According to (Allan & Lubel, 2022), Strategic Prioritization includes both Demand Management and Resource Allocation. Demand Management is concerned with prioritizing and managing the intake of work, ensuring it aligns with the organization's strategic objectives. Strategic Prioritization is not solely reliant on methodology and data. While establishing a detailed structure and plan is crucial, it is equally important to consider priorities beyond the quantitative aspects. This is where the art of the Strategic Prioritization process becomes essential, involving a careful evaluation of each initiative or project based on its value ("What benefits will this bring to the company?") and complexity ("Do we have the necessary resources, time, and budget to complete it?"). According to Ferreira (2017), the process of prioritizing projects is influenced by the values and preferences of the decision-makers. However, in addition to these subjective factors, more specific criteria, such as financial considerations, strategic alignment, risk assessment, urgency, stakeholder commitment, and technical expertise, also play a significant role in the decision-making process.

Additionally, A common error that business professionals may encounter when moving from strategy formulation to execution is attempting to tackle too many initiatives simultaneously. While each strategic initiative may contribute to the overall business strategy, assuming that all of them should be pursued can be a mistake. Seasoned strategists understand that spreading efforts and resources too thin across numerous projects can lead to exhaustion, confusion, and ultimately, unsuccessful outcomes. Research by Bridges Business Consultancy reveals that nearly half of organizations fail to achieve their strategic objectives, underscoring the importance of prioritization to maximize the likelihood of goal attainment. (Cote, 2022). Therefore, determining the most prioritized 5 bold moves strategy in Telkom Indonesia is of significant urgency due to several critical reasons such as : Business Transformation as Telkom Indonesia is currently undergoing a major business transformation through the implementation of the 5 bold moves strategy. Identifying the most prioritized moves is essential to guide the company's strategic direction and ensure the successful execution of the transformation plan. (Cote, 2022). The initial phase of prioritization is linked to the strategic direction of the organization, which outlines the path a company will take to gain a competitive advantage (Kluyver and Pearce, 2010, as cited in Santos et al., 2021). The telecommunications industry in Indonesia is highly competitive, with multiple players vying for market share and customer loyalty, hence, Telkom can strengthen its competitive position and differentiate itself from competitors. Another reason is related to the rapidly evolving digital landscape presents numerous opportunities for Telkom Indonesia to expand its

business and capture new markets which will allow the company to seize these opportunities and capitalize on emerging trends in the industry which maintain its relevance in the market. According to Fernbach et al., (2014), priority planning results in cost savings by making decisions that involve trade-offs between various goals due to limited resources and opportunity costs. This statement shows that by prioritizing the most effective moves strategy can optimize its investments, allocate resources strategically, and enhance its financial outcomes which might have a direct impact on Telkom Indonesia's financial performance and growth prospects the company. Cote (2022) describes that it is imperative to prioritize strategic in assisting the success of the process of implementing strategy formulation. Thus, it is expected that the chosen bold moves will define the company's approach to digitalization and ensure a successful transition into a leading digital telco. As the digital transformation journey is vital for Telkom Indonesia to adapt to the digital age and stay ahead in the competitive landscape.

D. Previous Research

Naesens et al. (2007) study used AHP to determine the factors influencing companies in evaluating strategic fit for collaboration, using criteria and sub-criteria such as company characteristics (company structure, financial strength, image, general company characteristic), competitive advantage (product/service, general competitive advantage), internal process (operational, tactical, strategic), and external parameters (product service specific, industry-specific, general external parameters). Lee et al. (2022) found that competitive advantage, core competencies, and strategic alliance partner selection significantly impact alliance performance. Švárová and Vrchota (2014) also stated that service-oriented businesses have the highest strategic coherence with competitiveness. Therefore, this research focuses on the criteria and sub-criteria of competitive advantage (product/service, general competitive advantage) in selecting the most prioritized five bold moves strategy in Telkom Indonesia.

The Vargas (2010) study used AHP to select and prioritize projects in a portfolio, considering criteria and sub-criteria like stakeholder commitment (team commitment, organizational commitment, project manager commitment), financial aspects (return on investment, profit, net present value), strategic aspects (improves ability to compete in international markets, improves internal processes, improves reputation), and other criteria (lower risks (threats) for the organization, urgency, internal technical knowledge). This study showed that the most crucial criterion in project selection is strategic, with a weighting value of 0.4604 (exact calculation of the Eigenvector). Hence, this research adopts the criteria and sub-criteria of strategic from Vargas (2010). However, the stakeholder commitment criterion is also chosen because according to Vargas (2010), stakeholder commitment is a set of criteria designed to evaluate the extent of stakeholder dedication to the project. Projects with higher commitment from stakeholders are given higher priority. The assessment of commitment can be broad, considering all stakeholders as a unified group, or it can be broken down into various stakeholder groups, such as customer commitment, organizational commitment, and regulatory bodies. As a state-owned enterprise, it is essential for Telkom to consider these aspects to achieve its targets and address industry challenges while meeting shareholder aspirations.

Furthermore, the study by Guler and Buyukozkan (2019) used AHP to analyze digital transformation strategies, considering criteria and sub-criteria such as talent (digital learning, digital human resources, employee engagement), governance (analytics capabilities, information quality, data and content management), and future readiness (process digitization, change culture, leaders' attitude). The talent criterion is chosen because digital transformation heavily relies on skilled individuals. Building a competent team comprising technology, data, and process experts who can collaborate effectively, along with capable leaders to drive change, is a critical factor for successful digital transformation. Although exceptional talent doesn't guarantee success, the absence of it significantly increases the likelihood of failure (Davenport and Redman, 2020, as cited in Guerra et al., 2023).

Figure 1. Research Framework: Naesens et al, (2007); Vargas, R. (2010); Guler and Buyukozkan (2019) developed by researchers.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research relates to the issues researched by the author to provide in-depth understanding with a qualitative approach. Various previous studies have categorized the use of AHP as qualitative research. Qualitative research aims to understand and explore the meaning of groups or individuals around humanitarian or social issues (Creswell, 2016). AHP qualitative research does not rule out the possibility of being supported by quantitative data (Cheng and Li, 2001). In addition, qualitative research emphasizes the depth of thinking to answer the problems faced and in general regarding the main phenomena explored in the research locations and research participants (Creswell, 2016). The main balance that supports AHP is qualitative research namely; 1) AHP is not used to generalize a situation because this method only quantifies ideas, feelings, and emotions based on subjective judgment to be presented on a numerical scale; 2) AHP research is not related to the issue of reliability in measuring a variable; and 3) The use of in-depth hierarchical analysis to solve problems in a decision making is in line with the qualitative approach. Thus, this research is to find out the main criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives in determining the most effective five bold moves strategy in Telkom to be prioritized.

The research framework in this study to identify the criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives in addressing the research questions. There are four criteria, namely: Stakeholder Commitment (Organizational Commitment, Customer Commitments, Regulatory Bodies), Competitive Advantage (Product Service, General Competitive Advantage), Talent (Digital Learning, Digital Human Resources, Employee Engagement), and Strategic (Improves Ability to Compete in International Markets, Improves Internal Process, Improves Reputation). These four criteria are used to determine the prioritization of choices in The Most Prioritize Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia.

Data Collection Method

Primary data is used in this research, obtained from field research with both primary and secondary sources. The data collection technique employed in this study is a questionnaire or survey using a pairwise comparison scale for each element, aiming to obtain responses as requested by the users (Kisworo and Sofana, 2017 cited in Rufandi, 2019). The questionnaires were distributed by involving participants/informants/sources. The AHP questionnaire differs from a general questionnaire because the AHP questionnaire is structured in the form of pairwise and hierarchical comparison questions among dimensions. The scale for pairwise comparison assessment used ranges from 1 to 9 (Saaty, 1990), where 1 = equal, 2 = weak, 3 = moderate, 4 = moderate plus, 5 = strong, 6 = strong plus, 7 = very strong, 8 = very, very strong, 9 = extreme.

A paper for publication in Journal must contain a title, names and affiliations of the authors, a list of keywords, a brief abstract at the beginning, a conclusion section at the end of the main body, and a list of references that follows the conclusion section. The

manuscript must be typewritten with single spacing and wide margins, on a single side of an A4 paper. The text should be in single-column format. Times New Roman typeface should be used throughout. A handwritten manuscript will not be accepted for review. Each page should be numbered beginning with the title page to facilitate review. AHP does not require a large number of participants. In a study on car purchasing decision-making using AHP, the participants involved only thirteen sales managers, each with more than ten years of experience and relevance in the field (Byun, 2001). The AHP method can be conducted with several participants, or even with one participant who is appropriate and possesses relevant experience (Cheng and Li, 2001). The determination of the sample size used in this research follows Roscoe's suggestion (Sekaran and Bougie, 2016) that a sample size larger than 30 and less than 500 is suitable for most studies. The more respondents, the better the results obtained.

RESULTS

Hierarchical structure of criteria, sub-criteria, and main alternatives in The Most Prioritize Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia are presented in Table 4.2. The processed data using the expert choice tool, AHP, resulted in the following hierarchy structure and weight values. The criteria "competitive advantage" and "strategic" became the main criteria with weight values of 0.318 and 0.303, respectively. They were followed by the criteria "stakeholder commitment" with a weight value of 0.207, and "talent" with a weight value of 0.171.

The primary consideration in the competitive advantage criterion is to address the industry challenges and shareholders' aspirations for achieving the future business of Telkom Indonesia, including the acceleration of the company's equity growth and closing the gap of 100 trillion by 2024. Additionally, there are various fundamental challenges faced by global telecommunications companies, such as negative headwinds, low revenue growth, increased capital expenditure, stagnant profitability, potential for low valuation improvement, and declining market capital share compared to tech players. Therefore, the research findings are in line with the challenges faced by Telkom Indonesia. Within the competitive advantage criterion, the main sub-criteria is "product service" with a weight value of 0.508, while the sub-criteria "general competitive advantage" also plays an important role with a weight value of 0.492.

Furthermore, the strategic criterion has a weight value of 0.303, with the main sub-criterion being "improves ability to compete in international markets" with a weight value of 0.348. This aligns with the research findings and Telkom Indonesia's strategy of structure delayering. Structure delayering is implemented to develop a focused business portfolio and separate specific core businesses from the parent company, thereby creating greater value compared to the integrated Telco model. Other leading telecommunications companies have also undergone structural changes to unlock value by involving external investors and buyers. For example, Jio established a digital HoldCo by separating its assets and operations into subsidiaries, Telefonica plans to create a new unit for its digital assets and infrastructure to unlock value (B2B services, InfraCo, and geographical OpCos), and Telstra launched B2B DigiCo in 2019 and announced plans to create two InfraCos and ServeCo in 2021.

Therefore, Telkom Indonesia has taken a significant step called Five Bold Moves to address the current challenges in the Telco industry by considering the hierarchy of criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives in this research. The main alternatives in The Most Prioritize Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia indicate that "fixed and mobile collaboration (FMC)" and "data center Co" have a dominant influence in the hierarchy structure with weight values of 0.262 and 0.212, respectively. This is because FMC is implemented to minimize inefficiencies between fixed and mobile broadband to maximize the company's value due to separate strategies, potential cannibalization, and double resource potential. Furthermore, FMC will have positive impacts such as increasing brand awareness for Telkom Indonesia and Telkomsel, reducing capex and opex through consolidation and eliminating function duplications internally and for customers, and providing unique competitive advantages and differentiation factors compared to competitors.

Regarding data center Co, it has a main strategy that needs to be accelerated to maximize TDE's performance, including utilizing partnerships with hyperscalers as the main tenant and forming partnerships with global DC players, designing appropriate governance for coherent negotiations with hyperscalers as a group, accelerating investment strategies to enter regional DC markets through joint ventures with Singtel in Batam to serve the Singapore market, adopting an independent DC Co-led strategy supported by Telkom Group's synergy.

Table I. Hierarchy Criteria, Sub-criteria, and Alternative The Most Prioritize Five Bold Moves Strategy in Telkom Indonesia.

Criteria	Sub-criteria		FMC	INFRA CO	DC CO	B2B DITS CO	DIGI CO	
Competitive Advantage	0.318	Product Service	0.508	0.046	0.026	0.038	0.029	0.025
		General Competitive Advantage	0.492	0.044	0.036	0.031	0.026	0.026
Total Criteria Competitive Advantage			0.09	0.062	0.069	0.055	0.051	
Strategic	0.303	Improves Ability to Compete in International Markets	0.348	0.017	0.013	0.03	0.026	0.023
		Improves Reputation	0.335	0.024	0.018	0.029	0.018	0.016
		Improves Internal Process	0.317	0.027	0.019	0.013	0.016	0.012
Total Criteria Strategic			0.068	0.05	0.072	0.06	0.051	
Stakeholder Commitment	0.207	Organizational Commitment	0.363	0.021	0.013	0.015	0.011	0.014
		Customer Commitment	0.349	0.02	0.009	0.012	0.01	0.012
		Regulatory Bodies	0.287	0.017	0.015	0.012	0.01	0.01
Total Criteria Stakeholder Commitment			0.058	0.037	0.039	0.031	0.036	
Talent	0.171	Employee Engagement	0.576	0.028	0.016	0.015	0.015	0.012
		Digital Human Resource	0.424	0.018	0.012	0.017	0.02	0.015
Total Criteria Talent			0.046	0.028	0.032	0.035	0.027	
Alternative			0.262	0.177	0.212	0.181	0.165	
Overall Inconsistency			0.01					

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

From the discussion on the selection of the most prioritized five bold moves strategies in Telkom Indonesia using the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) method, the following conclusions can be drawn to answer the research question:

- a. Competitive advantage and strategic become the main criteria. These criteria should be prioritized to address industry challenges and achieve future business aspirations.
- b. The main sub-criteria within the competitive advantage criterion are "product service" and "general competitive advantage." Telkom should focus on continuous innovation and improving its products and services to maintain a competitive edge. The strategic criterion should emphasize "improves ability to compete in international markets." Telkom needs to develop strategies to enter new markets and form partnerships with global players to expand its presence in the international telecommunications market.
- c. The main alternatives among the five bold moves are "fixed mobile convergence (FMC)" and "data center Co (DC co)." Telkom should encourage collaboration between fixed and mobile teams to maximize market share and optimize its data center capabilities to leverage partnerships.
- d. The impact of knowing the most prioritized five bold moves strategies for Telkom Indonesia can be significant. By understanding and focusing on FMC and DC co, Telkom can enhance its competitive advantage and improve its ability to compete in international markets. FMC allows Telkom to leverage its fixed and mobile services to create synergies and capture a larger market share. On the other hand, DC co presents opportunities for Telkom to collaborate with other network and cloud providers, providing business opportunities and potential revenue growth
- e. To be consistent in the future, Telkom Indonesia needs to implement several improvements:
 - 1) Emphasize product and service innovation to stay ahead of the competition and meet evolving customer needs.
 - 2) Strengthen its ability to compete in international markets by entering new markets and forming strategic partnerships with global players.
 - 3) Optimize its data center capabilities through collaborations with hyperscale data center partners and efficient management of data center resources.
 - 4) Foster a culture of agility and adaptability within the organization to respond to market changes effectively.
 - 5) Monitor industry trends and competitors regularly to identify growth opportunities and make necessary adjustments to maintain competitiveness.

Recommendation

The implications of this research reveal the hierarchy of the most prioritized five bold moves strategy in Telkom Indonesia. This information is crucial in providing insights into the main criteria, sub-criteria, and alternatives to consider for Telkom Indonesia's future strategies after implementing the organizational transformation of the five bold moves. Furthermore, this research can serve as a benchmark for improving the criteria and sub-criteria of Telkom Indonesia. Based on the research findings, the following recommendations can be made:

1. Consider adding additional criteria and sub-criteria in similar research studies.
2. Combine the Analytic Hierarchy Process method with other Multi-Criteria Decision Making techniques.

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